

Brochure for the collection of soil samples in cork oak forests

Introduction

The analysis of soil samples collected in cork oak forests allows knowing the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil, constituting, together with foliar analysis, support for the most appropriate fertilization recommendation.

However, although this practice is not new, it is not a practice followed by the majority of forestry producers, who, although viewing cork production as a lucrative economic activity, do not understand the need to analyze the nutritional status of forest stands and carry out necessary fertilization and soil amendments.

The collection of soil samples must be carried out well in advance of the application of fertilizers, being advisable the period in which the soil has a moisture content that allows this operation to be carried out, which generally happens in autumn - winter.

If the land is not uniform, it should be divided into relatively homogeneous plots with regard to color, slope, drainage and type of forest management.

Samples must not be taken in wet areas, near paths, houses, stables or in places that have been occupied with manure, sludge, fertilizers, ashes or other products.

Lessons learned

Thus, to sensitize forestry producers, a publicity leaflet was prepared, which is available in paper and online, in accessible and easy-to-understand language. The leaflet defines when the analysis should be carried out, how it should be carried out depending on the type of existing forest stand: before the stand, in a young stand, in an adult stand or even in modern irrigated cork oak plantations. It also defines what equipment is necessary for the correct collection of samples and how to pack and send them to the laboratory to obtain the results.

Figura 1. Material necessário à colheita das amostras de terra

- No caso de se utilizar uma sonda, é necessário possuir também um punho e uma marreta Fig. 1 e Fig. 2.

Figura 2.
 Pormenor do punho e da sonda de meia cana

Figure 1. Upper photos - needed material to gather soil samples. When using a soil sampler probe, a sledgehammer is needed. Lower photo - use of the soil sampler probe on the field.

Figura 3. Pontos de recolha de subamostras de terra

Figure 2. Locations where the soil samples were gathered showing the gathering pattern.

For further information contact

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Further information

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/nutrition-and-fertilization-cork-oak-forest-nutrisuber_en

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